

The Benefit of Using Multimedia Projector in English Language Teaching Classroom

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Abstract

The research article presents the benefit of using multimedia projector by teachers of English language. In the era of modern science and technology, the latest portion has been added in language teaching. With the progress of technology, new innovations are being brought up in language teaching. At present, language teachers are using multimedia projector to facilitate the teaching process. Along with text books, language teachers are likely to use pictures, audio clips, videos, power point slides, in language classrooms by the multimedia projector. The purpose of this study is to investigate the benefits that the language teachers as well as the learners get in using multimedia projector in teaching English language. A qualitative process has been followed to collect the data of this research. It has been found that the use of multimedia projector supports both the teacher and the students in learning language skills. As well as this research shows that by using the relevant audio-visual substance how the teachers overcome from teacher oriented classrooms.

Keywords: Multimedia projector, audio-visual aids, dynamic, benefits, ELT, facilitate.

INTRODUCTION

From the beginning of twenty first century a dramatic change has been emerged in the field language teaching classroom. Most of the classrooms are equipped with modern technology. Using multimedia projectors in English language teaching is very common and it makes the teaching and learning easier than the past. So the Multimedia projector has become the main focus of English language teaching classroom. It is undoubtedly true that the time has come to consider updating the language teaching styles, methods, techniques and technology as used the multimedia projector in the English language teaching classroom. Now, with only a laptop computer, a cable connection and a white board, a language teacher can accomplish a greater range of multimedia technology applications in any English language teaching classroom.

Language instructors are attempting to bring new novelties in their teaching to make their language teaching successful. Teaching language is very tough job and it is needed to be motivating enough to eliminate the anxiety of the students. Language teachers have a tendency to regulate various types of methods to teach language more efficiently and more successfully. Use of latest multimedia projector is often less expensive to maintain and use as an important via of teaching language. So with the quick development and availability of equipment, language teachers are incorporating various supplementary supports besides the text books to teach language.

Modern science technology can supply a wider diversity of devices available for use in English language classes

From audio recordings, graphics production and display software to videos available online, multimedia is constantly available from an wide range of sources. Never has a greater range of options been as readily available to English Language teachers all over the world. Various kinds of electronic machinery, multimedia projector, and computer, audio and video equipment are making the language teachers' mission lively and active. Language teachers are using multimedia projector to deliver their lectures and teach the target language to the learners making the class interesting.

This research plans to emphasize on the questions as to how language class can be effective and successful with the use of multimedia projectors. This research investigates how the language teachers, as well as learners, are benefitted from the multimedia projectors in language teaching and learning. This research gives a comprehensible analysis of the reason of using multimedia projectors in language teaching and its advantages from both teachers' and learners' point of views.

So, the use of multimedia projector in language teaching has become a widespread affair for the language teachers, most of the teachers do not know the usefulness of these. Nevertheless, this research will give an approach to the language teachers of using multimedia projector. It is anticipated that the findings of the study will help the language teachers to know better about the benefit of using multimedia projector in the classroom. As a result, this paper will be a prospect instruction for the English language teachers regarding the issue.

LITERATURE REVIEW

All over the world English language plays an essential role because of increasing a great many of English language learners and various kinds of teaching-learning techniques are followed. Among them the method of using multimedia projector or audio-visual aids in language teaching is mostly benefitted not only for the teacher but also the students. Pun (2013) investigated that how the teachers and students of English language are benefitted by using multimedia projector in the classroom. He highlights that the quick expansion of modern technology as likes multimedia that refers to computer-based applications, allow teacher and students to share their views and ideas. It is a combination of text, graphics, animation, video and sound. The utilization of multimedia technology has created a favorable situation in improving the attractiveness in English language teaching and learning (Pun, 2013).

In the present teaching coordination, another vital support for the teachers is PowerPoint slides. PowerPoint slides have become accepted among the teachers from all levels and disciplines. This instrument has made teaching more vibrant with attractive appearances along with multimedia projector equipment. Ozaslan & Maden (2013) analyzed a significant study where they establish that students learn better if resources are presented through the help of illustrations. Teachers also think that PowerPoint slides make the content more attractive which draw the attention of the students easily (p.42). Some people say and think that PowerPoint slides are not always helpful for teaching. It makes a hinder both the presenter and the viewers as the presenter deliberates more on the slides than the viewers. According to Norvig (2003), "PowerPoint makes it difficult to make exchange between presenter and viewers, to communicate ideas that do not efficiently fit into outline format" (as cited in Craig & Amernic, 2006. p. 157). However, Corbeil (2007) in his work found that learners prefer PowerPoint for their vividness, liveliness, clearness and interactivity. It assists the students to comprehend better as they can watch the visual with examples (p. 645).

In the very beginning of seventeen century a newly language teaching technique had appeared named 'The Silent Way' depend on the Cognitive Approach. The main motto of this process was that, learning is easier if the students discovers or generates rather than memorization and repetition what is to be learned; learning is benefitted by using physical objects and trouble solving joining the materials to be learned. In this method, there is use of multimedia to benefit the teaching. Teachers use sound color chart and color rod to teach the intentional language. Here every color symbolizes a sound. Teacher points a color in the color chart and the students pronounce the sound that is represented by the color itself. Thus the use of multimedia is fit with the method in teaching sounds (Richards & Rodgers, 1986, pp. 81-83).

Although the use of multimedia projector in language teaching has become a widely tendency to the English language teacher and trainers; there is not enough study on this issue, particularly in the Bangladeshi context. Mathew & Alidmat (2013) analyzed that the effectiveness of multimedia projectors in ELT in Middle East context. According to the authors, "Teaching and learning becomes monotonous when the language teachers are compelled to rely on the text books as the only source of language input" (p.88). There, they found how the use of multimedia projector helps the language teacher in ELT classroom at university level. They explored that the result of their work specifies that using multimedia projector in language teaching is helpful for both the teachers and the learners. Both the groups argued that it makes the class interesting and effective (pp.89-90).

Çakir (2006) found that use of video by the multimedia projector in English language teaching make sure genuine language effort to the learners. In addition, using content related videos helps the students to comprehend the thoughts and get in the actual concept on that subject matter. Moreover, students can give attention to the use of contextual language in the videos along with non-verbal characteristics of language that assists them to have better understanding of using target language (p. 67).

Kausar (2013) focused on significance of multimedia projector as well as audio visual aids for learning English and announced that the learners are facing numerous troubles in learning English language and think it is complex to learn English language except the use of any audio or visual aids. The work presented that audio visual aids should be used in an English language classroom to benefited teachers and learners

Cunning (2001) explored the benefit of using multimedia projector in language teaching states that video supplies stimuli to the students which benefits a chance to the learners to get a surroundings representation of the subject. Also the use of videos by multimedia projector helps the students to get a suggestion of the stress and rhythm sample of the targeting language. In addition, it permits the students to guess, assume and investigate the information of the subject matter (as cited in Koksai, 2004. P. 63). However, by watching a video, students get the chances of experiencing influential of language communication. As Secules, Herron, & Tomasello (1992) found, "Video offers language learners opportunities to see the dynamics of communication, and because such materials are widely available, it may offer a better and feasible option for listening comprehension (as cited in Long & Doughty, 2009).

At present use of image by multimedia projector in English language teaching classroom has become a frequent affair. Photographs are efficient additional supports in an ELT classroom. Using various appropriate images in classrooms makes the class

pleasant and enjoyable. It helps the teachers to show the satisfied of the classroom. Also, it makes the students more thoughtful and engaged in responsibilities. When images are used to present any topic to the students, it becomes more real and specific. Students can have a general idea of the lesson and can produce their views superior. It improves the students' understanding ability. Use of multimedia projector makes the learning more long-lasting than the use of traditional textbooks (Craig & Amernic, 2006. pp. 152-153).

Daniel (2013) discussed about the benefits of using multimedia projector in teaching English among learners. It creates curiosity for learning in the students, it is also save the time because it can give the detailed idea very much effectively and accurately, load of teacher is decreased, teacher can develop his/her personal English knowledge, new varieties of experience for students, it makes learning English very easy, it helps in concentrating the attention of students on the lesson (Daniel, 2013).

Multimedia projector in English language teaching classroom benefited the teachers to carry a dramatic and dynamic change in the class atmosphere as well as in the teaching techniques. Multimedia projector in the class, teachers can deliver a topic not only verbally but also visually that is much supportive for the students to give more concentration in the class. Students are also able to discuss together between the verbal and non-verbal as well as theoretical and material issues. There are some conceptual things in language which is tricky to explain verbally. The theme or topic may not be clear to the students and they can make effort to catch what the teacher is going to represent. Nevertheless, by using various kinds of picture and audio visuals, teachers can make the students understand better. If the verbal and visual things are shown together, students can get the information rapidly. Mayer (2001) argued that, if the instruction is given in the class using both words and visuals, learning become faster (as cited in Dolati, 2011, p. 6).

Reading is one of the prime and significant language skills, mainly for the pupils as they need to read numerous text books and resources throughout their whole educational time. Moreover, students generally do not hard work on reading as required. For this reason, the duty of the language teachers becomes hard. However, if the teacher can make the reading interesting incorporating visual aids, students may pay their attention to reading. If the teacher use multimedia projector in reading class that can be benefited the students and teachers in many ways. According to Yunus, Salehi & John (2013), use multimedia projector as visuals draw more attention among the students in reading. Various visual aids like images and videos help the students to understand the conceptual prospect of the text. Moreover, visual aids create a real relation between the readers and the text. It makes the reading process quicker and

lively. Readers think more attached with the text through multimedia projectors (pp. 114-15).

Among the four skills in English language writing is one of them. At this time, many eye-catching visuals are used to encourage the students in writing. Teachers utilize various multicolored illustrations for instructing creative writing. When a teacher give them a task of writing as well as any kind of composition, the students feel anxious and they show their disagree. Moreover, when the teacher shows them any kind of eye-catching and interesting thing and asks them to write little bit on that. Then they would write very interesting way according to teachers demand. So using videos by the multimedia projector is very mush essential in writing classroom. Moreover, images can be shown to persuade the learners for writing story. Halwani (2017) investigated that reading and writing would developed when teachers help the students by using multimedia projector as audio-visuals and student shyness would remove for showing the visuals. Students would read and write smoothly and spontaneously. (Halwani, 2017).

This is the age of communicative language teaching and learning so speaking is the most important language skill for this era. In the beginning, people thought that learning English language means to read the literary peach. However, the conception has been changed all over the world. At present, learning English language means the oral and verbal conversation with others. Communicating with others is the main purpose of learning English. For these reason highest priority has been given on speaking skill. Cakir (2006) investigated the significant of using multimedia projector to show the video for presentation and speaking skills. He discussed that dynamic observation enhances the learners' satisfaction and enjoyment as well as draws their concentration on the prime idea of the video presentation by multimedia projector. So, it is essential for learners to have a dynamic element in video teaching presentations. In the very beginning of the presentation the teacher will write the topics as well as discuss the main theme of the presentation then students will elaborately present it. After screening the asking queries the learners reply the questions verbally, or the learners may have notes in the time of video. For further elaborated text content learners are given a cue sheet or video guides and let them see and listen for correct and specific feature of the language. Moreover, it should be kept in mind that the level of the students should be taken into report and adjust the method along with their levels (p. 69). Among the four language skills, listening was the most difficult skill for the language teachers to teach. However, people did not try to understand the important of listening skill. For this reason in earlier English language teaching, listening skill was highly overlooked. However, with the emergence of science and technology, it has become very easier to the English language teacher.

At present, many kinds of visual materials are available to provide the students with native speaker's accent of listening English. By browsing internet any language teacher can collect relevant listening materials within a short time according to the learner's level. As a result, the use of multimedia projector in teaching listening skill has been enhanced according to its necessity. Presently the latest ELT teachers have been trained so that they can find out how to incorporate multimedia projector as audio-visual aids in language teaching (Ozkan, 2002, p. 39).

Earlier time teaching listening; the teachers needed to take appropriate ideas for the lesson they are going to teach in the class room. Firstly they had to set up the technical devices and adjust the materials. the Materials also should be justified according to the learners ability. When the teacher select some interesting type of listening materials then the students became very happy and they were encouraged to listen the audio and answer the questions that teacher asked.. Underwood (1989) explored, "In the pre-listening stage of a lesson it can reason "students to 'switch off' and did not try to do anything, and this in twisting diverts those who are trying to complete the assignment. All the learners should comprehend what they have to do before a teacher begins to run, read or speak the listening text" (as cited in Rosova, 2007, p. 34).

Vocabulary plays a vital role to learn the main four skills of a language so it is a crucial part of learning a language. If anybody wants to speak with others by using a certain language, he must be familiar with the vocabulary of that language. Moreover, language teaching cannot be fulfilled without teaching vocabulary of the target language. Therefore, vocabulary should be taught in the way that can a learner easily understand also able to use in listening, speaking, reading and writing. To teach the vocabulary multimedia projector is essential resource. If teacher use multimedia projector in English language teaching classrooms then the students can easily understand the how they will use the word appropriately. According to Allen, Kate & Marquez (2011), "Visual aids can add more interest to a presentation of vocabulary. Learners have an excitement to learn vocabulary. Multimedia projector facilitates learners to apply more logics at a time. An image can elicit more and more words". (p.5)

If the learners the teachers show positive impression toward the use of multimedia projector as audio-visual aids, they will be benefited in various ways. By using multimedia projector in the classroom, teachers can make the class interesting way. Multimedia projector brings difference in the classroom teaching which are useful to draw the concentration of the learners to the lessons. He has also given an example that, if the language teacher use various kinds of images related to the lesson of the class, the classes become dynamic as well as learners get the real idea of the topic. It is

beneficial to have something visuals in front of the learners so that they can comprehend the lesson well. (M. Al Mamun., 2014, p. 41)

METHODOLOGY

I have followed both qualitative and quantitative methods to conduct the research. It contains with observation, interview of the teachers and students.

Research Questions

This research aimed to find out the answers of the following questions:

1. How does multimedia projector benefited language teaching?
2. What are the teachers' perceptions about the use of multimedia projector in ELT classrooms?
3. In which point are the learners getting advantage from it?
4. What are the probable hindrances that teachers face in multimedia projector in classrooms?

Participants

The participants of this research were ten English language teachers from ten well-known school, college and university of Dhaka city who have been teaching English for more than six years. Besides, fifty students participated in the data collection process of those institutions' current students.

Method and Timeline

Many kinds of methods were followed to collect information with a number of tools. Firstly, the ten English language classes were surveyed within three weeks. A definite class inspection checklist was used to detect the information. Then ten experienced English faculty members have been interviewed by five days. They were asked readymade and finally the data was accomplished one day with the students.

Limitations

The research was carried out not more than six months. So time border was the most important constraint. In addition, the local-political condition unfavorably distressed the data collection procedure. However, the subjects of this study were from ten academic institutions which correspond to the whole situation of the use of multimedia projector in teaching and learning at English language teaching classrooms.

FINDINGS AND DATA ANALYSIS

The findings of the research have been investigated and arranged sequentially to the research question. The beginning part illustrates the finding from the class inspection along with sorting various vital issues that were discovered in a number of language classes. Second part shows the statistics accumulated from the teachers' interview. It includes the reply from the various language teachers and their skills. Here, the viewpoints of the learners of using multimedia projector and their effectiveness in learning language have been surveyed.

The ten English language classes that were surveyed to get the thoughts about the multimedia projector were benefitted with various visual and audio substances. Phonemic chart, songs, discussions etc were the most regular audio materials used in those classes. Pictures, video clips, movie clips, documentary etc were shown through the multimedia projector in the classes. Most of the time multimedia projectors were utilized in the spoken and listening classes. Ice breaking session or at the beginning of any class was the common time of the using multimedia projector. Besides, the projector was applied to offer the students with the right pronunciation. Also, to test the listening skills as well as to follow up activities of the learners audio clips were played.

Multimedia projectors in English language teaching classroom plays significant tasks to make a class cooperative and guide to make conversation. Sometimes the teacher used puzzled photograph those can be give detailed from various angles. The teacher asked every student about the puzzled photograph one by one. Among the learners there was a number of debate program also noticed. Agreements and disagreements conversation also happened. Some of classes also noticed argumentative speech. Finally the teacher talked about the topic. The use of the photograph facilitated the students to arise with ideas for the dialogue.

The teacher could openly initiate the issue but the use of the photograph benefitted the teacher to bring out ideas from the learners and guide them to the conversation. Therefore, the learners had plans of the topic earlier and help to develop their speaking abilities. In the undergraduate program, the teacher delivered a motivational video through the multimedia projector.

In the video there have man being physically disabled he was not only playing football, golf, drums but also swimming. End of the video, every student are asked by the teacher to express their views the about the video and students also expressed their thoughts according to the motivations they got from the video. So, to develop

their speaking skill it was a great opportunity for the students to as well as they became free with the teacher to discuss about the man and his firmness.

Approximately speaking and listening skills are shown by multimedia projector. Sometimes, the teacher used multimedia projector to listen English song to teach listening skill. In the starting of the class, the strategy of listening was discussed by the teacher. After playing a song students were asked to listen to the song attentively without taking notes. Then, they were asked to take note by listening the song second time. After that students were asked to share their understanding one by one about the song. So the class was both full of the speaking and listening skills as well as the students liked the song class was effectual and full of enjoyment. By this way teacher can engage the students.

Moreover, to teaching writing skill multimedia projector was also used. The teacher demonstrated the image of two rooms through multimedia projector and asked the students to discover the contrast of the two rooms. Then they asked to compose a comparison paragraph according to the pictures. So, multimedia projector was used to teach different language abilities by the language teachers. To remove the anxiety of the lecture based class multimedia projector plays a vital role as well as it also helped to draw the attention of the students.

I asked the reason of using multimedia projector in the classroom then one of the teachers responded that,

"I use multimedia projector to do the class enjoyable. Students feel bore when I give long lecture but if I use multimedia projector as well as relevant video of the topic then they become more attentive".

Then I asked a teacher about the challenges of using multimedia projector in the classroom. She replied,

"Sometimes I fall in some technical type of problem when I use projector in my classroom. Often I bring the materials through the pen drive but virus attack it or often video do not support at all. So I have to be shame in front of my students".

One the other hand few school teachers express their view about the problem of using multimedia projector in English language teaching classroom. A school teacher said that,

"Using multimedia projector sometime distracts students' interest, they also become habituated only to use visuals but our all examination system depends on reading and writing so after using more and more visuals they became addicted and feel bore to write and read ."

But most of the university teachers have been given almost same opinion on behalf of multimedia projector. One of them said that,

"Using multimedia projector in English language teaching classroom is very much beneficial because we give assignment our students and ask them to present the assignment through projector, when they ready the presentation in computer and perform it in front of all students and teachers it make smart and ready to face job interview"

To answer to the question, ten teachers approximately came with related response. They agreed that they use multimedia projector in their English classes. The common pictures and videos they use are phonemic chart with sound, English songs, audio clip of native conversation, short video clips documentaries, and pictures etc that are related to topics to facilitate their speaking and listening. Depending on the lessons and activities, they choose the materials.

To response the question about how speaking benefited by using multimedia projector, on student replied that,

"When a teacher asked to tell something on a topic suddenly or after five minutes brain storming, we feel nervous to tell but if we see any video on the given topic then it becomes very easy for us to tell few minutes."

Another student responded my question about writing. He said that,

"In writing skill we benefited highly by watching videos through multimedia projector. Basically in the case of creative writing, when a teacher asked us to write something on an unknown topic then we feel difficulties but if we watch any video or hear any audio so it becomes very easy to write any story or composition. "

All the students had the same opinion that multimedia projector assist them to learn language in different ways. They argued that multimedia projector also helps them to learn English language the correct pronunciation. In response of this question, students stated that multimedia projector plays essential tasks as well as benefited

their speaking skills. They mentioned that illustrations like images, posters and video clips generate ideas. Listening audio in English is helpful for practicing correct accent as well as to speak like a native speaker. Most of the students gave their opinion that watching video motivated them in reading in various ways. Some of them argued that multimedia projector helped the learners to assemble concepts for writings. Most of the students came with the same view that use of multimedia projector makes the class attractive and pleasurable. Only the teacher's lecture-oriented class becomes boring for the learners. However, many types of motivating videos can remove the boredom of the students. They can pay more concentration to the lesson as it becomes more interesting and enjoyable.

SUMMARY AND IMPLICATION

Exceeding argument frequently reveals the effectiveness of using multimedia projector in ELT classroom. So it is also clear with the purpose of article is to prove that different language teaching methods like Communicative Language Teaching and DM are highly supported by using multimedia projector. It is also noticed that when teacher use vibrant videos by multimedia projector students become greatly impressed and pleased. Some researchers talked about the challenges of using audio and video materials in language teaching. Based on the top of the discourse, a proposition can be prepared that 'English language teaching classroom becomes efficient and vibrant by the use of multimedia projector. Depend on the help of different reviews of the literature; this article has a mutual the result and outcomes of the research in an order to find out the correct reply of the research inquiries.

CONCLUSION

The final outcome of the research specifies that the multimedia projector encourages the students and benefited them to reduce their nervousness. Multimedia projector makes the classroom more dynamic and lively as the students can get actual English through it. This electronic device make an effort as indicates to the students that if they give a good response according to teachers' guidelines, their speaking fluency level up dramatically and they will be ready like a native speaker . Through the multimedia projector, students listening capability will be high if they listen the audio properly. Moreover, it is also stated that teachers can plans and performs various kinds of lingual events on the basis on the multimedia projector. As well as, students can note down when they are available in front of live multimedia projector.

If the instructor does not prepare or elect the visuals for listening and speaking skills appropriately then the thing will be defective, so teacher must design or select the materials carefully as the students can guess and understand the visuals perfectly. In

addition, enough informative programs should be performing as the students could discover their thought of spoken fluency. Technically trained teacher is needed to take the class with multimedia projector otherwise they will not maintain the class, so they have to know the use of computer as well as multimedia projector. Before performing the audio or video materials, the teacher should have checked the materials second time. If the materials are from internet then some unexpected tracks could be visualized that will be shameful for the teacher.

Finally it can be said that, benefit of using multimedia projector in English language teaching classroom cannot be described. The whole research paper represents and proves that using multimedia projector in ELT classroom is very essential as well as beneficial.

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